

Effect of Pile Thread Spacing on the Friction Resistance of Minipile

Asmadi, Rizal, Zeldi Muhardi, Satriyo Utomo, Helyanto,
Muhammad Rafani

Department of Civil Engineering, Politeknik Negeri Pontianak, Indonesia

ABSTRACT:

This study aims to determine the most effective type of pile foundation between threaded sleeve piles with a 10 cm spacing and threaded pile piles with a 20 cm spacing, focusing on their frictional bearing capacity. Test specimens were prepared using reinforced concrete with a compressive strength of K-350 kg/cm², reinforced with 4D10 mm longitudinal bars and Ø8-150 mm stirrups. Measurements of pile settlements were taken over several days to assess their behavior under load. Results indicated that piles with a 10 cm thread spacing exhibited a settlement of 3.7 mm on the first day, while those with a 20 cm spacing settled by 4.2 mm, with a percentage difference of 29.6%. The study concludes that rougher surfaces (tighter threads) yield greater frictional forces, thereby enhancing pile bearing capacity. Additionally, settlements tended to stabilize over time, with piles at 20 cm spacing experiencing a quicker cessation of settlement compared to those at 10 cm spacing. This research provides valuable insights for foundation engineering, material technology, and concrete construction practices. It also offers practical implications for the pile manufacturing industry.

Keywords: minipile, threaded pile, friction, bearing capacity, settlement.

Suggested Citation: Asmadi, Rizal, Z. Muhardi, S. Utomo, Helyanto, M. Rafani, I. Arianti, "Effect of Pile Thread Spacing on the Friction Resistance of Minipile," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 2(2), pp. 279-284, Mar-Apr 2024. DOI: [10.59324/ejaset.2024.2\(2\).19](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejaset.2024.2(2).19)

INTRODUCTION

The introduction should lay the ground-work for why the article is worth reading, and describe where the work fits within the existing literature. Introduce the novel elements of the paper in the introduction, thus providing motivation for the reader to penetrate the main text. Do not over-burden the reader by making the introduction too long. Get to the key parts of the paper sooner rather than later. Introduction should have no more than 15 lines. In this study, a comparison is made between two types of pile foundations with variations in the thread spacing [1-4], aiming to determine which pile is capable of withstanding a greater load. Pile foundations are constructed with dimensions of 15 cm x 15 cm and a length of 270 cm, differing only in the thread spacing. The first pile model features a 10 cm thread spacing, while the second model has a 20 cm thread spacing. The thread dimensions are planned to be 1 cm x 1 cm.

Testing involves driving the piles to a depth of 220 cm, followed by applying a load of 403.2 kg with uniform loading. The loading procedure is consistent for both types of test specimens. Observations on settlement are conducted over a period of 15 days with daily recordings.

The concrete used for the piles has a compressive strength of K-350 kg/cm² ($f'_c = 31.2$ MPa) and reinforced with 4D 10 mm longitudinal bars and with a diameter of Ø8-150 mm stirrups. Testing is carried out using a fixed loading method, where the load is placed on the pile foundation once it is installed [5].

Pile foundations have been widely utilized in peat soil, often in the form of plain concrete piles with high compressive strength. However, recent research has explored the use of threaded piles,

specifically helical piles, initially employed as anchors for communication transmission towers. These threaded piles have undergone further development to serve as foundations for building structures, capable of withstanding both vertical and lateral loads [6-8].

The helical shape of these piles provides several advantages, including enhanced load-bearing capacity and improved resistance to soil movement. By screwing the pile into the ground, it increases the surface area in contact with the soil, thereby increasing frictional resistance and improving stability. This makes helical piles particularly suitable for challenging soil conditions such as peat soil, where traditional plain concrete piles may encounter difficulties [9-10].

Moreover, the versatility of helical piles allows for their application in various construction projects, including buildings, bridges, and other infrastructure. Their ability to resist both compression and lateral forces makes them a valuable option for ensuring the stability and safety of structures built on peat soil or other challenging ground conditions [11-13].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Formwork

Making pile test specimens using formwork measuring 15 cm x 15 cm, 270 cm long made from 12 mm thick multiplex boards. The manufacture of plain and threaded piles is the same, the only difference is that the threaded stakes are given fins in the form of wood measuring 1 cm x 1 cm with a distance of 10 cm and a distance of 20 cm.

Figure 1. Formwork of Threaded Pile 1/1-10 cm and 1/1-20 cm

Figure 2. Formwork of Sample: a) Thread 10 cm, b) Thread 20 cm

Reinforcement

The reinforcement of the pile using 4 D 10 longitudinal bars and $\text{Ø}8 - 150$ stirrups, more details can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 3. Detail of Reinforcement

Figure 4. Sample Making: a) Reinforcement Assembly, b) Ready to Cast, c) Casting

Methods

Piles were driven into the ground with a hammer weighing 75 kg, to a depth of 220 cm, the remaining piles are left 50 cm above the ground surface for placing loads and installing dial gauges. Loading is carried out after 3 days of driving, the aim is to consolidate the soil around the piles, followed by loading by placing a concrete block weighing 403.20 kg on a loading table placed on piles. On the first day, observations of settlement data are recorded every hour, on the second and subsequent days observations of settlement data are recorded every 24 hours, until the settlement stopped.

Figure 5. Implementation: a) Pile Ready to Loaded, b) Dial Gauge Installation, c) Loading

RESULTS

Results of observations research on the influence of pile foundation thread distance 1/1-10 cm and 1/1-20 cm regarding the frictional resistance, rectangular cross-section measuring 15 cm x 15 cm; length 270 cm; with a loading weight of 403.20 kg; type of soil (clay); loading takes place at 07.00; observation of the settlement was carried out from 08.00 to 18.00; The results of observing the reduction in pile loading can be seen in table 1 as follows:

Table 1. Pile Settlement Accumulation

Days	Accumulation of Settlement (mm)	
	Thread Spacing 20 cm	Thread Spacing 10 cm
1	4,2	3,7
8:00	1,5	1,1
9:00	2,0	1,6
10:00	2,4	1,9
11:00	2,8	2,4
12:00	3,1	2,5
13:00	3,5	2,7
14:00	3,6	2,8
15:00	3,7	3,0
16:00	3,8	3,2
17:00	4,0	3,5
18:00	4,2	3,7
2	4,5	3,9
3	4,7	4,0
4	5,0	4,2
5	5,4	4,3
6	5,7	4,5
7	5,9	4,6
8	6,3	4,6
9	6,4	4,7
10	6,7	4,8
11	7,0	4,9
12	7,1	5,0
13	7,1	5,1
14	7,1	5,2
15	7,1	5,2
16	7,1	5,2

Figure 6. Accumulation of Pile Settlement

DISCUSSION

The pile settlement on the first day was quite large, reaching 4.2 mm for piles with a thread spacing of 20 cm, while for piles with a thread spacing of 10 cm the settlement value was 3.7 mm, so the difference in settlement between a thread spacing of 20 cm and a pile with a thread spacing of 10 cm was 0.6 mm. On the first day of loading, friction between the pile and the surrounding soil it was not too compacted so there were still gaps in the threads that had not yet been filled by soil, thereby reducing the frictional resistance of the pile. Meanwhile, on the second day and onwards there was still a settlement (see table), but the time period for the settlement was 24 hours, so that the settlement on the following day was not too large compared to at the beginning of the loading, it is possible that around the piles there was already compaction of the surrounding soil. The settlement stopped for a thread spacing of 20 cm occurred on day 12th, while the settlement stopped for piles with a thread spacing of 10 cm occurred on day 14th. This indicates that the greater the number of threads on the pile, the longer the settlement time, but the accumulated value of the settlement getting smaller. If you look at the results table, the biggest difference in decrease occurred on days 11th, 12th and day 13th. To see which of the two models of threaded piles is the most strongest in carrying the load, it can be seen in table 2.

Table 2. Maximum Settlement of the Pile

No	Pile Type	Settlement (mm)	Difference Settlement Max. (mm)
1	Thread spacing 20 cm	7.1	2.1 (12 th day)
2	Thread spacing 10 cm	5.0	

If we look at the settlement results of the two pile models as in the table above, the tighter thread spacing will carry a greater load, meaning that the tighter the threads are, the greater the friction will be to withstand the load, so the settlement will be smaller, and vice versa, the longer the thread distance, the smaller the frictional adhesion power, the smaller the load it can bear. If viewed from the perspective of settlement time, threaded piles with a spacing of 20 cm stop declining faster than piles with a thread distance of 10 cm, with a time difference of 2 days.

CONCLUSION

From this research that has been carried out, it can be concluded as follows:

Two types of piles are made with the same size, with a cross section of 15 cm x 15 cm with a length of 270 cm with a rectangular shape, with longitudinal reinforcement 4D 10 mm, Ø8-150 mm stirrups which are assembled using welding. At the top end there is a 6 mm thick steel plate as a cap. The compressive strength of the concrete used is K-350 kg/cm² ($f_c = 31.2$ MPa). Pile driven by 220 cm deep with the remaining length of 50 cm not embedded in the ground that is used for placing loads and dial gauge. The load weighing 403.20 kg is made of concrete blocks, loading is carried out after 3 days of driving with the aim of conditioning the soil around the pile.

The settlement in piles due to loading on the first day was 4.2 mm for piles with a threaded spacing of 20 cm, and 3.9 mm for piles with a threaded spacing of 10 cm. On the second to the twelfth day the settlement continued but was not too big. The difference in the largest settlement value between the two type was 2.1 mm, where the settlement in the 10 cm threaded spacing pile model was smaller than the 20 cm threaded spacing pile type, which occurred on day 12th. Settlement stops at a loading time of 12th days for piles with a threaded spacing of 20 cm and at a loading time of 14th days for piles with a threaded spacing of 10 cm.

The closer the thread distance, the rougher the surface of the pile, the greater the load the pile can carry, in other words, the greater the friction between the pile and the ground.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Our thanks to the Center for Research and Community Service at Politeknik Negeri Pontianak for research funding assistance so that this research could be carried out

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

No conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. A. Ghaly, J. Hanna, "Frictional resistance of threaded bars and threaded connections," *Journal of Geotechnical Engineering*, vol. 114, no. 8, pp. 859-878, 1998.
2. A. Mohejerani, D. Bosnjak, D. Bromwich, "Analysis and Design Methods of Screw Piles: A Review," *Soils and Foundations*, vol. 56, no. 1, pp. 115-128, 2016. DOI: [10.1016/j.sandf.2016.01.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sandf.2016.01.009)
3. S.N. Rao, Y.S.V.N. Prasad, M.D. Shetty, "The Behaviour of Model Screw Piles in Cohesive Soils," *J. Soil Found.*, vol. 31, no. 2, pp. 35–50, 1991. DOI: [10.3208/SANDF1972.31.2_35](https://doi.org/10.3208/SANDF1972.31.2_35)
4. M.H. Nasr, "Performance-based design for helical piles. In: Contemporary Topics in Deep Foundations," American Society of Civil Engineers, USA, 2009, pp.496–503. DOI: [10.1061/41021\(335\)62](https://doi.org/10.1061/41021(335)62)
5. M. Aydin, T. Bradka, D. Kort, "Osterberg cell load testing on helical piles," *Geo-Frontiers*, pp. 66–74, 2011. DOI: [10.1061/41165%28397%298](https://doi.org/10.1061/41165%28397%298)
6. C.C. Hird, S.A. Stanier, "Modelling helical screw piles in clay using a transparent soil," Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Physical Modeling in Geotechnics, Zurich, Switzerland, 2010, 28 June – 1 July. Taylor and Francis Group, London, 2010. pp.769–774. DOI: [10.1201/b10554-126](https://doi.org/10.1201/b10554-126)
7. R.M. Hoyt, S.P. Clemence, "Uplift capacity of helical anchors in soil," Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engineering, vol. 2. Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, 1989, pp. 1019–1022. DOI: [10.1139/cgj-2012-0350](https://doi.org/10.1139/cgj-2012-0350)
8. B. Livneh, M.H.M. Nagggar, "Axial testing and numerical modelling of square shaft helical piles under compressive and tensile loading," *Can. Geotech J.*, vol. 45, no. 8, pp. 1142–1155, 2008. DOI: [10.1139/T08-044](https://doi.org/10.1139/T08-044)
9. M. Sakr, "Installation and performance characteristics of high capacity helical piles in cohesionless soils," *Deep Found. J. (DFI)*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 39–57, 2011. DOI: [10.1179/dfi.2011.004](https://doi.org/10.1179/dfi.2011.004)
10. M. Sakr, "Lateral resistance of high capacity helical piles: case study," Proceedings of the 63rd Canadian Geotechnical and 6th Canadian Permafrost Conference. Calgary, Alberta, 12–16 September, 2010, pp.402–412. DOI: [10.1061/9780784480137.043](https://doi.org/10.1061/9780784480137.043)
11. M. Sakr, "Performance of helical piles in oil sand," *Can. Geotech. J.*, vol. 46, no. 9, pp. 1046–1061, 2009. DOI: [10.1139/T09-044](https://doi.org/10.1139/T09-044)
12. R. Schmidt, M. Nasr, "Screw piles: uses and considerations," *Struct. Mag.*, pp. 29–31, 2004.
13. J.E. Bowles, *Foundation Design and Analysis*, 5th ed. McGraw-Hill, USA. 1996.

